

Event Abstract

Pedigree of neurofibromatosis type 1 in Libyan patients and primer design of NF1 gene

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Background: neurofibromatosis type 1 is one of the most common genetic disorders and is caused by mutation in Nf1 gene, is characterized by its high mutation rate (about 50% of the cases are de novo). NF1 gene mutational analysis presents a considerable challenge because of its large size. This disease has been reported in several regions and cities of Libya, through the registry database in dermatology departments of Tripoli Central Hospital. The proportion of the disease in Libya is still not precisely defined.

Aim: the aim of present study is to determine average of manifestation of this disease and Primer design for nf1 gene in order to identifying the nature of genetic mutations that is most prevalent in the Libyan population.

Methods: in this study, we conducted an interview with nine patients who were referred to the Department of dermatology at the central Hospital Tripoli. We designed a primer of 58 exon to serialize the gene on the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) by the bioinformatics tool primer blast and multiplex pcr to 4 exon which most Hight rate of mutation with fast PCR.

Result: Through this research we were able to prove that the neurofibromatosis type 1 is widespread in Libyans.

Conclusion: This research provides a study of the emergence of disease and the design of the initiator of this gene, through an integrated methodology. The results of this research are important for sequencing the detection of gene mutations in the Libyan patients. This research is the first step to detect the most common mutations among the Libyans.

Keywords: Neurofibromatosis, NF1 Gene, Primer Design, Pedigree.

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